

Preparation, FTIR Spectroscopy and Ferroelectric Properties of ZnBi₄Ti₄O₁₅ Ceramic

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ABSTRACT

The present paper reveals Bismuth Layered-structure ferroelectrics (BLSFs) of Zinc Bismuth Titanate (ZnBi₄Ti₄O₁₅ – ZBT) ferroelectric ceramics prepared by conventional solid-state route process. The combination of raw oxide powders are ZnO, Bi₂O₃, and TiO₂ with 99.9% purity and mixed according to stoichiometric portion. This mixed powder calcinated at 950 °C for 4 hours and sintered at 1100 °C for 2 hours. The absorption peaks at ~ 540, ~ 820 and ~ 1040 cm⁻¹ are measured by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy. The ferroelectric properties are studied and determined remnant polarization (2P_r) and coercive field (2E_c) by P-E hysteresis loop.

Keywords: Conventional solid-state route process, Stoichiometry, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy and P-E hysteresis loop.

INTRODUCTION

Zinc Bismuth Titanate (ZBT) is one of the Bismuth Layered-Structure Ferroelectrics (BLSFs) Oxide ceramics. ZBT ferroelectric material belonging to Aurivillius structure (AS) family, it is invented by Arivillius [1-2]. This type of materials have more attention in present years with their low dielectric constant, high transition temperature, low coercive field, large anisotropy in the electro mechanical coupling factor 'K' and good fatigue endurance [3-5]. These properties made the system to be essential for potential utilization in many devices. The chemical condition for AS family is (Bi₂O₂)⁺²(A_{m-1}B_mO_{3m+1})⁻², here 'A' indicates mono, di, or tri valent ions which as K⁺, Na⁺, Ba²⁺, Ca²⁺, Pb²⁺, Sr²⁺, Zn²⁺ Bi³⁺ and Lanthanides (Ln³⁺); 'B' shows tetra, penta or hexa valent ions such as Ti⁴⁺, Ta⁵⁺, Nb⁵⁺, W⁶⁺, Mo⁶⁺, etc.; and m = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 reveal to the no. of BO₆ octahedra between layers of (Bi₂O₂)⁺² [6-9]. Characteristics of ferroelectrics get in the BLSF ceramics by the BO₆ octahedra in perovskite layers through the c-axis. The BLSF compounds are widely applicable in capacitor, transducer and memory devices [10, 11]. The present material ZBT have m = 4 member of AS family of orthorhombic structure with space group of A2₁am. In this family Zn and Bi ions at A-site and Ti is at B-site of the perovskite (A_{m-1}B_mO_{3m+1})⁻² layer and shows the condition as [(Bi₂O₂)⁺² ((ZnBi₂)Ti₄O₁₃)⁻²]. ZBT indicates anisotropic ferroelectricity, this is strongly applied with the crystal structure, because of the (m = 4) there is no polarization by c-axis and there is a mirror plane perpendicular to the axis reveals polarization through a and b-axis [12]. In the present work used conventional solid-state route method to synthesis of ZBT sample.

PREPARATION AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCESS

The ferroelectric material of Zinc Bismuth Titanate (ZnBi₄Ti₄O₁₅ – abbreviated as ZBT) compounds were prepared by conventional solid-state route (CSSR) method. The initial raw compounds were ZnO, Bi₂O₃, and TiO₂ of Oxide powders with 99.9% purity. In the starting process raw powders were weighed with an electric balance and then mixed according to stoichiometric portion. For homogeneity the mixed powder was kept into Teflon jars of Ball miller and grinded by 200 rpm for 10 to 12 hours with ZrO₂ balls 1:10 ratio using an acetone as media. The grinded powder was placed in a hot air oven for drying at 80 °C. Dried mixed powder was taken in aluminium crucibles were kept in an Electronic Silicon Carbide Programmable Furnace and then calcinated at 950 °C for 4 hours from 30 to 950 °C (~ 10° per minute). The calcinated powder ground thoroughly and milled again. The binder PVA of 3% adding to milled powder and inserted into circular compact disk and applied presser up to 250 Mpa. At last the pellets were made with size of 0.2 cm thickness and 1 cm diameter. Finally pellets were sintered at 1100 °C for 2 hours by utilising Electronic Silicon Carbide Programmable Furnace with heating rate of 5 °C/min. The properties of Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy studied in the limit of 400 to 4000

cm^{-1} through a resolution of 2 cm^{-2} . The measurements of ferroelectric properties were analysed by using P-E hysteresis loop tracer.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The ZBT calcinated powder of FTIR spectrum was shown in Figure (1) and the spectrum shown few absorption peaks from 1600 to 650 cm^{-1} . The less intense peak at 1040 cm^{-1} corresponds to O–H groups, and the existence of the peak may be due to bending of bonds. It was also observed that there was one broad absorption band at 820 cm^{-1} in the spectrum which was attributed to Ti–O stretching vibrations arising from the strongly covalently bonded $(\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3)^{2+}$ layers [13, 14]. The sharp absorption peaks at 540 cm^{-1} was attributed to Ti–O stretching vibrations. A similar observation was made by Choi et al. on the CBT samples synthesized by a sol-gel method [15].

Figure 1: TIR Spectra of ZBT Ceramics

The ferroelectric hysteresis loops of zinc bismuth titanate obtained under a maximum applied electric field of 40 KV/cm. The P-E loops were recorded at a frequency of 50 Hz at room temperature and shown figure (2). The remnant polarizations of ferroelectric domains were parallel to the pole field, while the piezoelectric properties of ferroelectric ceramics were dominated by intrinsic lattice contributions and extrinsic contributions from movements of non- 180° domain walls. In general, the bismuth oxide layered structured ferroelectric (BLSF) plays an important role of an insulating layer by compensating the space charge effect. There had been an accumulation of oxygen vacancies near domain boundaries that cause pinning to reduce remnant polarization [16] and the ferroelectric behavior was clearly observed. The remnant polarization ($2P_r$) and coercive field ($2E_c$) for ZBT ceramic were found to be $8.50 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ and $22.76 \text{ KV}/\text{cm}$.

Figure 2: P-E hysteresis Loop for ZBT Ceramic

CONCLUSSION

The Zinc Bismuth Titanate ($\text{ZnBi}_4\text{Ti}_4\text{O}_{15}$ – ZBT) four-layered ferroelectric ceramic is prepared via conventional solid-state route method. The raw oxide powders of ZnO , Bi_2O_3 , and TiO_2 are weighed, combined by stoichiometric ratio and milled for 10 to 12 hours. The mixed raw powder is calcinated at $950\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 4 hours with step size $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ and sintered at $1100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 hours using Electronic Silicon Carbide Programmable Furnace. The absorption modes of FTIR spectrum at around 540 , 820 and 1040 cm^{-1} are studied by Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy. The ferroelectric measurements are identified according to P-E hysteresis curve and calculated remnant polarization ($2P_r$) as $8.50\text{ }\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ and coercive field (E_c) as $22.76\text{ kV}/\text{cm}$.

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